

Modelling of Autoclave Curing of a Porous Polymer

Paper Number : 1382

Bhishm Dewangan

(PhD scholar)

Under the Supervision of

Dr Nilanjan Das Chakladar

Advanced Composites Engineering Laboratory

Mechanical Engineering Department

Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur

West Bengal, India. 721302

□ Outline of presentation

- Introduction
- Literature Review
- Flowchart
- Materials
- Methodology
- Periodic Boundary and RVE Modelling
- Concept of Dynamic RVE
- Autoclave Curing
- Conclusion and Future Work
- Selected References

Introduction

- High demand of defect-free advanced fibre polymer composites

Trapped bubble

*Advanced Composites Engineering Laboratory,
Mechanical Engineering Department, IIT Kharagpur

Others curing Defects:

Spring back

Warpage

Literature review

RVE modelling

(Heng et al. 2022)

Periodic boundary condition

(Omairey et al. 2019)

Porosity on composites

(Vajari et al. 2014)

Residual stress on curing

(Yuan et al. 2018)

(Hudson et al 2021)

Flow chart of work

Materials and materials models

Fourier heat conduction model:

$$K_{xx} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + K_{yy} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + K_{zz} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \dot{q} = \rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}$$

$$\dot{q} = \rho_r H_r \frac{d\alpha}{dt}$$

Cure kinetics model (Zhang et al. 2009):

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^m)(1 - \alpha)^n$$

Arrhenius equation: $k_i = A_i e^{\left(-\frac{E_i}{RT}\right)}$

- K_{xx} , K_{yy} and K_{zz} = thermal conductivity (W/mK)
- k_i = cure rate constant (per second)
- A_i = pre exponential factor (per second)
- E_i = activation energy (J/mol)
- R = universal gas constant ($J \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)
- T = absolute temperature in kelvin
- \dot{q} = internal heat generated flux (W/m^3)
- H_r = total heat reaction (J/Kg)
- α = degree of cure

Properties of epoxy (*Zhang et al. (2009) and *Substech datasheet) :

Density (kg/m^3), ρ	1225
Elastic modulus (MPa), E	2500
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.3
Specific heat (J/kgK), C_p	967
Thermal conductivity (W/mK), $K_{xx} = K_{yy} = K_{zz}$	0.191
Coefficient of thermal expansion ($^{\circ}C^{-1}$)	50×10^{-6}

Material :

Epoxy : Araldite LY1564
Hardener : Aradur 22962

Mixing ratio :

Epoxy: Hardener = 4:1

Cure kinetics parameters of epoxy (Zhang et al. 2009):

A_1 (sec^{-1})	20.77
A_2 (sec^{-1})	0.821
E_1 ($J \cdot mol$)	38330
E_2 ($J \cdot mol$)	20000
m	0.786
n	3.207
R ($J \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)	8.314
H_r ($J \cdot kg^{-1}$)	277000

Methodology

Modelling of randomly distributed pores inside an RVE:

Assumptions:

- Spherical pores.
- Location and diameter of pores are random.
- Pores do not intersect each other
- Intersection of pores with RVE boundary is neglected

Diameter of spherical pores (Vajari et al. 2014) = 20 to 50 μm

Structural Periodic Boundary Condition (PBC)

Implementation of PBC (Tian et al 2019):

Mesh size 12.5 μm (C3D4)

□ Step 1: Categorization of node

- Inner face (excluding node on common edges and corners)
- Inner edge (excluding nodes of corners)
- Corner

□ Step 2: Three reference points

- RP1 and RP2 for pure shear loading
- RP3 for pure tensile loading

□ Step 3: linear multipoint constraint equation on each node of boundaries (*Abaqus manual)

$$u_i^{k+} - u_i^{k-} - u_i^{\text{RP}} = 0$$

PBC constraint equations are **automated** in Abaqus via a **user-defined python script**.

Structural RVE Homogenization + UMAT

To determine the effective properties of RVE:

- 1) $\epsilon_{kk} = \bar{\epsilon}_{kk}$ and $\epsilon_{ij} = 0$ for tensile deformation
- 2) $\epsilon_{kk} = 0$ and $\epsilon_{ij} = \bar{\epsilon}_{ij}/2$ for shear deformation here $i, j, k = 1, 2$ and 3 and $i \neq j$

Total no of mesh elements in RVE = 253,636
Total no of constraint equation (PBC) = 3,783

Structural RVE Homogenization + UMAT

Isotropic linear elastic model (assumed quasi-isotropy)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda + 2\mu & \lambda & \lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \lambda & \lambda + 2\mu & \lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \lambda & \lambda & \lambda + 2\mu & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \mu & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mu & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mu \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{33} \\ 2\epsilon_{23} \\ 2\epsilon_{13} \\ 2\epsilon_{12} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where λ and μ are lame's parameters and given by:

$$\mu = G = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)}$$

$$\lambda = \frac{E\nu}{(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)}$$

Where ν , E , G are Poisson's ratio, elastic modulus and shear modulus.

UMAT with proposed 'multilinear elasticity'

A python script is written to automate execution of proposed material model in abaqus

Structural RVE Homogenization + UMAT

Single element verification with UMAT

Single element mesh size = 0.25 mm (C3D8)
Total no of constraint equation (PBC) = 21

Mesh sensitivity parametric analysis for no of divisions in UMAT

Thermal PBC and Thermal RVE Homogenization

Effective thermal conductivity tensor $\langle k \rangle_{ij}$:

$$\langle k \rangle_{ij} = - \frac{\langle q \rangle_i}{\nabla T_j}$$

$$\nabla T_j = \frac{\Delta \bar{T}}{L_j}$$

$$\langle k \rangle_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} k_{11} & k_{12} & k_{13} \\ k_{21} & k_{22} & k_{23} \\ k_{31} & k_{32} & k_{33} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where,

$\langle q \rangle_i$ = Effective heat flux vector

∇T_j = Temperature gradient vector

$\Delta \bar{T}$ = Imposed temperature boundary condition

L_j = Side length of the RVE the x_j direction

$$T^{i+} - T^{i-} - T^{RP} = 0$$

$$T^{RP} = \Delta \bar{T}$$

PBC constraint equations are **automated** in Abaqus via a **user-defined python script**.

Heat flux (HFL)
(mW/mm²)

Temperature
(°C)

Concept of Dynamic RVE

(a)

Porosity at different location have different distribution represented in 6 RVEs

(b)

\varnothing 15 mm
t = 4 mm

Macro scale domain with Dynamic RVE

Dynamic RVE is generated in the Abaqus by python scripting to automate preprocessing.

Structural vs coupled thermo-structural homogenized cure model

Only structural homogenized curing

Coupled thermo-structural homogenized curing

Autoclave curing

In-house built Autoclave (w/ CF Composites, India)

Conclusions

- Periodic boundary conditions with structural and thermal homogenization of RVE has been implemented.
- As number of multilinear divisions on UMAT increases, accuracy of results increases. For 10, 20, 50 divisions, accuracy of results is same, so based on CPU time 10 division is suitable for analysis.
- With an increase in porosity by 1% at micro scale, thermal conductivity of RVE decreases by 1.3%.
- A dynamic RVE approach is proposed and coupled with thermo-structural homogenized cure model.

Next plan of work:

- Incorporation of reinforcement to simulate curing of fibre reinforced polymer composite.
- Experimental validation of Macro scale FE model for tensile and flexural test will be performed.

Publication:

- 1) **B. Dewangan**, and N.D. Chakladar (2023). Effects of porosity on the cure kinetics and residual stress of a porous polymer. Materials Today Communications. Vol. 35, pp-105711.

Source of Funding:

- 1) IIT/SRIC/ISIRD/2019-2020/29 – IIT Kharagpur, ISIRD Scheme
- 2) IIT Kharagpur Doctoral Scheme

Selected references

- Hudson TB, Follis PJ, Pinakidis JJ, Sreekantamurthy T, Palmieri FL. Porosity detection and localization during composite cure inside an autoclave using ultrasonic inspection. **Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing**. 2021;147.
- Fu YT, Yao XF, Gao XH. Micro-mesoscopic prediction of void defect in 3D braided composites. **Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing**. 2021;147.
- Centea T, Hubert P. Measuring the impregnation of an out-of-autoclave prepreg by micro-CT. **Composites Science and Technology**. 2011;71(5):593-9.
- Cai H, Ye JJ, Shi JW, Wang YW, Shi Y, Huang B, et al. A new two-step modelling strategy for random micro-fiber reinforced composites with consideration of primary pores. **Composites Science and Technology**. 2022;218.
- Yang L, Yan Y, Ran ZG, Liu YJ. A new method for generating random fibre distributions for fibre reinforced composites. **Composites Science and Technology**. 2013;76:14-20.
- Tian WL, Qi LH, Chao XJ, Liang JH, Fu MW. Periodic boundary condition and its numerical implementation algorithm for the evaluation of effective mechanical properties of the composites with complicated micro-structures. **Composites Part B: Engineering**. 2019;162:1-10.
- Yuan ZY, Wang YJ, Yang GG, Tang AF, Yang ZC, Li SJ, et al. Evolution of curing residual stresses in composite using multi-scale method. **Composites Part B: Engineering**. 2018;155:49-61.
- Ashouri Vajari D, González C, Llorca J, Legartha BN. A numerical study of the influence of microvoids in the transverse mechanical response of unidirectional composites. **Composites Science and Technology**. 2014;97:46-54.
- Hernandez S, Sket F, Molina-Aldareguia JM, Gonzalez C, Llorca J. Effect of curing cycle on void distribution and interlaminar shear strength in polymer-matrix composites. **Composites Science and Technology**. 2011;71(10):1331-41.